

EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISATION OF THE PROGRESSIVE FAILURE OF GRID-SCORED SANDWICH STRUCTURES IN WIND TURBINE BLADES

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1 Introduction

Wind turbine blades are typically manufactured using a combination of different composite material configurations including sandwich structures. The aerodynamical requirements typically lead to a blade design where the aerofoil outer shape is made with single or double curved sandwich shells. This implies that the sandwich shell constituents need to be draped in the production process to follow the geometry. This is usually not a problem for the face sheets, since these are made of thin layers of glass or carbon fibre fabrics, but the core materials are usually delivered as thick plates of foam (or balsa wood) that cannot be fitted directly to the geometry. To accommodate for this, the materials are cut in small blocks and attached to a thin carrier fabric, which can then be draped. This type of core is known as "grid-scored", see Fig. 1. If the manufacturing process is based on resin transfer moulding, which is the typical production method for wind turbine blades, resin passes through these scores, thus creating a resin grid within the foam material. Since the resin is much stiffer than the foam, the presence of the grid will affect the local stiffness and load transfer of the core material. This in turn will change the stress distribution locally, and induce local stress concentrations in the interfaces between the different constituents. These stress concentrations may jeopardize the structural integrity of the composite sandwich shells and lead to failure.

1.1 Aim of work

Failure characterisation of composite structures, including both monolithic and sandwich laminates, is rarely straightforward and receives widespread

attention throughout the research community [1, 2]. For the case of sandwich structures, the global load-deflection response can in most cases be analysed numerically with high accuracy even for very complex load cases. However, the accurate prediction of failure, extending from initiation to complete loss of strength, is more difficult and must in all cases be supported by experimental investigations. A reliable methodology for predicting the progressive failure sequence of composite structures from initial localized failure and beyond has yet to be developed [3, 4]. Since the composite sandwich shell configuration investigated in this work, like most other composite materials, exhibits brittle failure with almost no margin of safety offered through ductility, the mechanisms leading to failure initiation and propagation must be understood, and a reliable prediction analysis method needs to be established. For example, failure initiates locally in the sandwich shell resin bridges at a lower load level than the observed non-linear load-displacement transition monitored for a simple uniaxial tension test as shown in Fig. 2. Thus, such failure onset phenomena might occur under normal blade operating conditions, which may contribute to failure of the entire sandwich structure when loaded in a multi-axial configuration. The ability to predict the initiation and the later growth of such initiated damages is important for predicting the performance of the grid-scored sandwich configuration and developing reliable designs. The aim of the work presented is to investigate the initiation and progression of failure in a grid-scored sandwich laminate configuration experimentally when subjected to either uni- and multi-axial quasi static loading conditions, and furthermore obtain a

phenomenological model capable of outlining the progressive failure sequence.

3 Limitations

The crack initiation in the resin bridges described above has so far only been observed, when the sandwich panels are loaded in either in-plane tension or transverse shear. Thus, the present study is limited only to investigate the failure sequence of the sandwich panels loaded in combinations of these, since the work still is in progress. Investigations on the failure behaviour in compression are ongoing. Further, the explained crack initiation also motivates investigations of the fatigue behaviour of the structure, but the presented observations are only valid for quasi-static loading conditions.

4 Experimental setup

Since grid-scored sandwich structures used in wind turbine blades are subjected to multi-axial loading conditions, a multi-axial testing facility has been developed to enable a failure characterization with realistic loading conditions, see Fig. 3. Thus, the loading conditions realized on the sandwich panel mimic the local loading conditions occurring in the wind turbine blade, see Fig. 4, which was established as part of the work in [5]. As illustrated by the failure sequence of the tension specimen in Fig. 2, failure initiates in the resin grid in-situ the core of the sandwich laminate, which visualises as white spots through the face sheets. However, the subsequent crack propagation into the foam is not visually detectable on the outer surface of the structure and the initiation of cracks requires continuous visual inspection. Thus to facilitate a systematic identification and monitoring of the initiation of cracks and their subsequent propagation in-situ the specimen, acoustic emission (AE) measurements [6] have been conducted on the uni-axially loaded tension specimen, shown in Fig. 2. The result is used to support the failure characterization of the grid-scored sandwich structure, when subjected to the more realistic multi-axial loading conditions. Primarily AE readings are used to monitor the progression of damage in real time (in terms of accumulated hits and events) as the test is performed and further to localise the source of crack initiation and growth. As explained in [7], various types of signal processing techniques can be

adopted to characterise the AE signals and relate them to the different failure modes occurring in the monitored specimen. The simplest approach is to classify the signal based on a single parameter, which also have been chosen in this study in terms of the energy level and frequency. In order to identify the indicative responses from the onset of resin cracks in the multi-axial loaded specimen, the uni-axial tension specimen has initially been monitored by a 2-channel AE system. The AE history of the tension specimen is shown in Fig. 5 in terms of accumulated numbers of hits and energy. Further Fig. 6 shows the amplitude and energy of each recorded event. The results indicate that AE readings are observed at even low load levels, but that a significant increase in events occurs around 30 kN, where the presence of the first resin crack initiations also takes place. Further the frequency response of the events with high energy is found around 50 kHz, as shown in Fig. 7. Thus, it is seen that the crack initiation can be identified by the AE measurements from the high energy releases with a frequency around 50 kHz. The subsequent crack propagation into the foam did however not seem to be detectable from the AE signals, hence this experimental evidence so far only can serve as identification of failure initiation of the grid-scored sandwich structure.

To facilitate the multi-axial failure investigation of the grid-scored sandwich structure a special cruciform-like specimen has been developed suitable for the setup shown in Fig. 3. The design allows a load introduction into the gauge zone, which represent the single curved panel shown in Fig. 4. In the present investigations a radius of curvature of 750 mm is chosen. GFRP in a Triax layup is used for the face sheets, PVC H60 is used for the core material and epoxy is used as resin system. The prepared specimen is shown in Fig. 8 and with strain gauge and acoustic sensor instrumentation in Fig. 9.

5 Experimental results

The loading conditions for the present investigations are applied such that the transverse in-plane load, P_T , is applied at a fixed ratio compared to the longitudinal in-plane load, P_L .

$$P_T = P_L/4 \quad (1)$$

Similarly the moment is applied at a fixed ratio;

$$M = -0.002P_T \quad (2)$$

where the sign convention follow Fig. 4.

The onset of resin cracks was, similar to the uni-axial tension specimen, observed as the first failure event for the multi-axial loaded specimen. The same indicative acoustic response, shown in Fig. 10, was observed at $P_L = 90$ kN, which from (1) and (2) means $P_L = 22.5$ kN and $M = -45$ Nm. Further, the AE measurements with high energy showed the characteristic frequency response around 50 kHz. The longitudinal and transverse strain on the top and bottom of the panel in the gauge zone, respectively, are shown in Fig. 11. In similarity to the uni-axial tension test, a normal strain around 5000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ in the same direction as the resin slit was observed to initiate the cracks in the resin. Further, as the load increased no indication of changes in failure sequence compared to the uni-axial test due to the multi-axial conditions were observed. The main difference observed in comparison to the outlined sequence in Fig. 2 was the subsequent crack propagation into the foam core, which could not be monitored on the multi-axial specimen, since no free edges were present in the vicinity of the resin grid, where cracks initiated. Further, the test was stopped, when strains close to matrix yielding of the face sheets was obtained, which explains the lack of significant nonlinear behavior on the force-strain curves in Fig. 11.

6 Phenomenological model

The experimental observations and results are intended as input to a phenomenological model describing the failure sequence of the grid-scored sandwich structure. Since the work still is in progress, the model will at present state only serve to explain the failure sequence qualitatively;

- 1) Crack initiation in resin brides
 - a. Governed by the straining of the face sheets in same direction as the score in the sandwich core
- 2) Crack propagation into foam core
 - a. Only visually identified in uni-axial loaded beam specimens
- 3) Matrix yielding in face sheets

- a. The multi-axial loading conditions do not seem to influence the failure sequence. Thus the load carrying capacity remains although cracks are present in the resin grid.

4) Ultimate failure of face sheets

Before quantitative results can be obtained from the model, a more comprehensive failure study is required as outlined in the future work section. The observed sequence suggests, however, that a more crack insensitive design can be obtained since physical based knowledge on the criterion for the resin cracks initiation and propagation into the foam can be taken into account.

5 Discussion and conclusion

The present work shows how the bi-axial tension failure sequence of the grid-scored sandwich panel has been monitored, both by visual inspection, strain gauge measurements and AE readings. The presented AE measurements were performed by a two channel system, which only allows a linear localisation between the two sensors. Given the geometry of the multi-axially loaded specimen a larger system would have been preferred to allow localisation of crack initiation and growth on the entire region of the gauge zone instead of only in between the two sensors. Regardless the limitations on localisation, it was found that the onset of failure in the resin grid could be identified from the acoustic signals, both in terms of energy and frequency, which aids the monitoring, when subjecting the panel to fatigue loading conditions. In that perspective it is assumed that the observed quasi-static failure onset mode in the resin bridges is required to occur, since the AE response most properly changes with the occurrence of a different failure onset mode. Further, the observations served as preliminary input to a phenomenological model, which aids in assessing the structures integrity when loaded in realistic loading conditions both before and after the onset of failure.

5.1 Future work

As explained the present results are limited only to outline the failure sequence of the grid-scored sandwich structure, when loaded quasi-static in bi-axial tension in combination with a transverse moment. Thus, a characterisation of the failure

behaviour in compression is still required with and without the presence of resin grid cracks in order to investigate the structures sensitivity to the presence of the resin grid. Further, investigations in fatigue, especially to fully reversed cycles are required to identify potential preliminary failure.

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Fig. 1: The grid-scored sandwich structure

Fig. 2: The failure sequence of a tension specimen

Fig. 3: The multi-axial experimental setup, encompassing in-plane bi-axial loading combined with bending in the horizontal direction.

Fig. 4: The multi-axial loading conditions realized in the panel by the multi-axial test setup.

Fig. 5: The accumulated number of hits and energy vs. load for the tension specimen

Fig. 6: The amplitude and energy of each measured event in the tension specimen

Fig. 7: The Frequency response shown compared to the energy of the events detected by the AE measurements

Fig. 8: The Cruciform specimen design

Fig. 9: The instrumented specimen showing failure initiation in the resin grid and in the vicinity of the ply drops

Fig. 10: Acoustic emission response of the multi-axial loaded specimen

Fig. 11: The strain gauge readings in the gauge zone

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